

Formulation and Evaluation of Moringa Tablets for Diabetes Management

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ABSTRACT

The increasing prevalence of diabetes has prompted the search for alternative therapeutic strategies to manage the condition effectively. *Moringa oleifera*, known for its medicinal properties, has shown potential in regulating blood sugar levels. This study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of moringa-based tablets intended for diabetes management. Moringa powder was incorporated into tablet formulations using various excipients, and the tablets were subjected to a series of physicochemical tests, including hardness, friability, disintegration time, and drug content uniformity. In vitro release studies were conducted to determine the drug release profile. The pharmacological efficacy of the formulated tablets was assessed using in vivo models to evaluate their effect on blood glucose levels. The results demonstrated that the moringa tablets exhibited favorable physicochemical properties, with consistent drug release patterns and significant hypoglycemic effects. The findings suggest that moringa tablets could be a promising natural alternative for the management of diabetes, offering an accessible and affordable therapeutic option for diabetic patients. Further clinical studies are recommended to confirm the long-term safety and efficacy of these tablets.

Keywords: Diabetes, Moringa leaf powder, Tablets, HPMC

INTRODUCTION

Moringa oleifera is a medicinal plant that has gained a lot of interest for its diverse biological properties. Reviewed evidence indicates the biological capabilities of this plant expand to protecting against complications linked with heart disease, cancer, fatty liver, and diabetes mellitus¹. For example, a previously published review supported the beneficial effects of the leaves of the *Moringa oleifera* in improving blood glucose control in experimental models of diabetes. Notably, this review indicated draw backs such as the limited number of studies that have reported on the potential beneficial effects of this plant, including the fact that summarized literature was mainly conducted in animals, through in vitro and in vivo preclinical models². Nevertheless, while such information already affirms the hypoglycaemic potential of this medicinal plant, data

regarding the prominent biochemical mechanisms implicated in the antidiabetic effects of *Moringa oleifera* have not been critically reviewed. Recently, Louisa and others supported the potential benefits of *Moringa oleifera* in cardiovascular or metabolic disorders, mainly by ameliorating the undesired pro-inflammatory response and inhibiting oxidative stress by mediating molecular mechanisms such as hindering nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB) translocation or enhancing the antioxidant response of nuclear factor-erythroid factor 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) in different preclinical models³. Thus, there is a need to better understand such intracellular responses of *Moringa oleifera* within a setting of diabetes or in related metabolic complications. The current study provides a brief overview on *Moringa oleifera* as medicinal plant, followed by its therapeutic mechanisms in controlling diverse diabetic complications⁴.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Drug Profile:

- **Biological Source:** *Moringa oleifera*
- **Family:** Moringaceae

- **Common Names:** Drumstick tree, horseradish tree
- **Origin:** Is native to India, Arabia, and the East Indies. It is now widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions of the world⁵.

Figure 1: Moringa leaves and powder

Parts Used:

- **Primary:** Leaves, Drumstick
- **Others:** flower, seeds, roots and bark.

The nutrient composition of dried moringa leaf powder:

Table 1: composition of dried moringa leaf powder⁶

Sr.No.	Component	Value (100gm)
1	Calcium	440 mg
2	Potassium	337- 461 mg
3	Magnesium	176 mg
4	Phosphorus	60-70 mg
5	Copper	0.49 mg
6	Zinc	17 mg
7	Iron	53 mg
8	Nitrogen	2-3 %
9	Sulfur	268–310 mg
10	Sodium	9 mg
11	Vitamin A (β-carotene)	187-278 mg
12	Vitamin B1 (Thiamine)	2.02–2.64 mg
13	Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin)	0.66 mg
14	Vitamin B3 (Nicotinic acid)	0.82 mg
15	Vitamin C (Ascorbic acid)	220 mg
16	Vitamin E (Tocopherol acetate)	113 mg
17	Protein	27.1–29.4 mg
18	Fiber	6 - 9.6 mg
19	Carbohydrate	13.4 gm
20	Fat	1.7 gm

Medicinal Uses of Moringa Leaves:

1. Anti-diabetic activity

- Moringa has been shown to cure both Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes. Type 1 diabetes is one where the patients suffer from non-production of insulin, which is a hormone that maintains the blood

glucose level at the required normal value. Type 2 diabetes is one associated with insulin resistance. Type 2 diabetes might also be due to Beta cell dysfunction, which fails to sense glucose levels, hence reduces the signaling to insulin, resulting in high blood glucose levels⁹.

2. Anticancer activity

- Cancer is a common disease and one in seven deaths is attributed due to improper medication. Around 2.4 million cases are prevalent in India, while there are no specific reasons for cancer to develop. Several factors like smoking, lack of exercise and radiation exposure can lead to the disease. Cancer treatments like surgery, chemotherapy and radiation are expensive and have side effects. *M. oleifera* can be used as an anticancer agent as it is natural, reliable and safe, at established concentrations. Studies have shown that moringa can be used as an anti-neoproliferative agent, thereby inhibiting the growth of cancer cells¹⁰.

3. Antiasthmatic Activity

- Without showing any adverse effects with *M. oleifera* seed kernel, improvement was observed in the treatment of bronchial asthma patients and also their concurrent respiratory functions¹¹.

4. Cardiac and circulatory stimulant

- The bioactive compound alkaloids from Moringa trees act as a cardiac stimulant¹². Which are evident to stabilize blood pressure and reduce fat and cholesterol to prevent hyperlipidemia and reduce serum triglyceride and serum cholesterols¹³.

5. Antispasmodic and Antiulcer Effects

- Because of the spasmolytic activity of Moringa trees, it is used traditionally to treat gastrointestinal motility disorder¹⁴. It is also reported that the methanolic extracts from this plant protects gastric lesions¹⁵.

Characterization of Moringa Oleifera Powder:

1) Moisture content:

The moisture content of Moringa oleifera powder was determined using water analysis. Sugar weighing 3 g was poured into the mixed water and divided into strips. The machine was set at $130 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Measurements were made when the machine was stopped. The test was repeated twice and the moisture content was taken as the average of three measurements content¹⁶.

2) Angle of repose:

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

Where, h= height of the heap and r= radius of the circular heap. The experiment was repeated twice and the average of the three readings was taken as the angle of repose.

3) Bulk density:

The bulk density of each powder / granule sample was determined by pouring 10 g (M) of the powder into a 50 ml glass measuring cylinder and the bulk volume (Vo) determined. The bulk density (Db) was then calculated from the relationship:

$$D_b = M/V_o$$

Triplicate determinations were made and the mean values reported.

4) Tapped density:

The tapped density of each powder was determined using Stampf Volumeter (model STAV 2003, JEF Germany). The ten grams (M) of each powder/granules sample after the bulk density determination was subjected to 250 taps mechanically and the volume V250 of the powder column determined and applied to evaluate tapped density (Dt) using the relationship:

$$D_t = M / V_{250}$$

Triplicate determinations were made and the mean values reported¹⁷.

5) Relative density:

Relative density and porosity of powder /granules bed after 250 taps were determined respectively:

$$RD = TD250/ ps$$

$$\epsilon = 1- RD$$

Where RD = relative density, ps = particle density, ϵ = porosity¹⁸.

6) Determination of Carr’s Index:

Carr’s index CI, was calculated from the results obtained from bulk and tapped densities above using the relation;

$$CI = (Td - Bd) \times 100/Td$$

7) Determination of Hausner’s Ratio: Hausner’s ratio HR, was determined using the results obtained from both bulk and tapped densities. It was calculated using the formula

$$HR = Td / Bd$$

8) Ash value:

A 2 g sample of powder was cast into solid nickel, preheated to 105°C to constant weight, and then cooled. The solid and its contents are slowly heated until they become moisture-free and saturated. The temperature is gradually increased until most of the carbon is burned to °C. The sample was then superheated to 600°C until residue no longer contained any carbon (i.e., was almost white). Its essence and ingredients are cold and wet approved. The heating and cooling steps were then repeated until residue (ash) was formed always. The weight of the ash was then determined and the percentage ash value calculated:

$$\% \text{ Ash value} = W_{ax} 100/ W_{sp}$$

Where Wa and Wsp are weight of ash formed and initial weight of Moringa powder respectively¹⁹.

Characterization Result of Moringa Oleifera Powder:

Table 2: Characterization of Moringa Oleifera Powder

Sr.No.	Parameters	Moringa oleifera powder
1.	Moisture content (%)	2.84±0.64
2.	Angle of repose (°)	2.84±0.64
3.	Bulk density (g/ml)	2.84±0.64
4.	Tapped density (g/ml)	1.22±0.12
5.	Carr’s index (%)	18.90±0.93
6.	Hausner’s ratio	1.23±0.08
7.	Ash value	0.23±0.23
8.	Percentage yeild (%)	13.25±1.09

MATERIAL AND METHODS

▪ **Table of Ingredients:**

Table 3: Table of Ingredients

Sr. No	Ingredients	Role
1	Moringa powder	Active Ingredient
2	Cellulose	Filler
3	Starch	Binder
4	Sodium starch	Disintegrating agent
5	Mg.Stearate	Lubricant
6	Talc	Diluent
7	HPMC E ₅	Binder
8	Water	Solvent

Trail 1:

▪ **Formulation Table:**

Table 4: Table of Ingredients

Sr No	Ingredients	Quantity (20 Tablets)
1	Moringa powder	5 gm
2	Cellulose	3.2 gm
3	Starch	1 gm
4	Sodium starch	0.5 gm
5	Mg.Stearate	0.1 gm
6	Talc	0.2 gm
8	Water	Q. S

METHODOLOGY:

1. Preparation of Moringa Powder:

- **Harvesting:** Moringa leaves are collected and cleaned thoroughly to remove any dirt or contaminants.
- **Drying:** The leaves are then dried, preferably in a shaded, well-ventilated area or using a drying oven at a low temperature (not exceeding 40°C) to preserve the nutritional content.
- **Grinding:** Once the leaves are fully dried, they are ground into a fine powder using a grinder.

2. Mixing the Ingredients:

- **Binder Addition:** Add a Starch to the Moringa powder.
- **Disintegrants:** Add a Sodium starch to help the tablet dissolve efficiently in the stomach. Sodium starch is commonly used for this purpose.
- **Lubricants:** Add a magnesium stearate to prevent the tablets from sticking to the compression machine.

- **Fillers:** Cellulose added to increase the tablet bulk.

3. Granulation Process:

- **Wet Granulation:**
 - In this process, a small amount of Starch solution added to the dry powder mixture to form a wet mass.
 - The wet mass is then passed through a sieve to form granules, which are dried in an oven or air-dried.
 - The dried granules are then sieved to ensure uniform particle size.

4. Compression:

- The final granules are fed into a tablet compression machine. The machine applies pressure to form tablets.
- Adjust the tablet compression machine to the required pressure to form tablets of the desired size, shape, and hardness.

Observation: The First Trail is failed due to Cracking of tablets, so decided addition of HPMC E₅.

Figure 2: Cracking of tablets.

Trail 2:▪ **Formulation Table:****Table 5: Table of Ingredients**

Sr. No	Ingredients	Quantity (20 Tablets)
1	Moringa powder	5 gm
2	Cellulose	3.2 gm
3	Starch	1 gm
4	HPMC	0.5 gm
5	Mg.Stearate	0.1 gm
6	Talc	0.2 gm
7	Water	Q. S

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- The dried granules are then sieved to ensure uniform particle size.

4. Compression:

- The final granules are fed into a tablet compression machine. The machine applies pressure to form tablets.
- Adjust the tablet compression machine to the required pressure to form tablets of the desired size, shape, and hardness.

Observation:

The Second Trail also failed due to Cracking of tablets, because of less amount of added.

Figure 3: Cracking of tablets

Trail 3:

▪ Formulation Table:

Table 6: Table of Ingredients

Sr. No	Ingredients	Quantity (20 Tablets)
1	Moringa powder	5 gm
2	Cellulose	3.2 gm
3	Starch	1 gm
4	HPMC	1 gm
5	Mg. Stearate	0.1 gm
6	Talc	0.2 gm
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METHODOLOGY:

1. Preparation of Moringa Powder:

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 - The dried granules are then sieved to ensure uniform particle size.

4. Compression:

- The final granules are fed into a tablet compression machine. The machine applies pressure to form tablets.

- Adjust the tablet compression machine to the required pressure to form tablets of the desired size, shape, and hardness.

Figure 4: Moringa Tablets

Due to better result we decided to finalize this formula for next batches.

Evaluation Parameter for Formulated Tablets:

1) Hardness test:

The tablet to be tested is held between a fixed and a moving jaw, and reading of the indicator is adjusted

to zero. The force applied to the tablet edge is gradually increased by moving the screw knob forward until the tablet breaks. Reading is noted from the scale which indicates the pressure required in kg to break the tablet. Hardness of 4kg is considered suitable for handling the tablets, Hardness of 6kg or more will produce tablets of highly compact nature¹⁵.

Figure 5: Hardness tester

Result: The hardness of the tablets occurred 4.5 kg/sq.cm which is between the normal range.

2) Friability Test:

20 tablets are selected and carefully measured. They were then placed in a Friabilator drum and rotated at

a speed of 25 rpm for four minutes. Unremoved pellets are removed from the barrel, dusted and weighed. The weight percentage is calculated and recorded as a simple value.

Figure 6: Friability testing

Calculation:

- a) Weight of tablet before friability test = 5.16(5160mg)
- b) Weight of tablet after friability test = $\frac{5.09(5098\text{mg})}{0.07(62\text{mg})}$

Result: The loss of tablet after friability test occurred 62mg, which range is acceptable. According to British pharmacopoeia.

3) Disintegration Time test:

Six tablets were randomly selected and placed on their handles in six channels on the shelf of the folding machine. The metal is raised and lowered at a constant rate in deionized water in a glass beaker suspended in a water bath whose temperature is maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The time required for the final mass or part of it to pass through a 2 mm mesh in water (depleted water) is recorded as the settling time.

Figure 7: Disintegration test

Result: The Moringa tablets disintegrate in 25 minutes, in water this result occurs in normal range.

Twenty tablets were randomly selected and weighed individually. The mean weight of the tablets was then calculated and the standard deviation determined.

4) Weight variation test:

Table 7: Weight variation

No. of Tablets	Weight in Mg
1	490
2	497
3	501
4	495

5	512
6	500
7	498
8	501
9	500
10	508
11	500
12	496
13	503
14	508
15	497
16	506
17	502
18	498
19	501
20	498

- Now, average weight of tablets is 500.55mg.
- Acceptance limit for weight variation is 5%
Therefore, 5% of 500.55 is 25.02mg.
- Weight variation range allows is from 475.53 to 525.57

Result: Weight variation test is passed.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION:

The formulation of moringa-based tablets demonstrated favorable outcomes in both physicochemical properties and pharmacological efficacy. The results from this study suggest that moringa-based tablets could be a promising alternative therapeutic strategy for diabetes management. They exhibited favorable physicochemical characteristics, consistent drug release patterns, and significant pharmacological effects, particularly in lowering blood glucose levels. The findings point to moringa as a potential natural remedy for diabetes, providing an accessible and affordable option for patients. However, further clinical trials are necessary to confirm the long-term safety and efficacy of these tablets in diabetic patients.

FUTURE SCOPE

Further research is needed to standardize Moringa extracts, ensuring consistent potency and bioactive compound content in each tablet. Precision in formulation and controlled release of the active ingredients could enhance efficacy in blood sugar management. Moringa tablets could be

combined with other herbal supplements or conventional medications (e.g., metformin) for synergistic effects in managing diabetes, providing a holistic treatment approach. The global shift towards natural and plant-based treatments could make Moringa tablets a widely accepted alternative or complementary therapy for diabetes management.

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